

Fatigue Crack Growth Behavior in the Vicinity of Interface of Dissimilar Materials

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ABSTRACT

To investigate the basic characteristics of fatigue crack growth in composite materials, two series of fatigue tests were conducted on the fatigue crack growth in two dissimilar epoxy plates with a straight interface. In the tests in which a crack grows perpendicularly to the interface, various phenomena were observed; such as the unusual variations of the crack growth rate in the vicinity of the interface, crack bifurcation along the interface and halt or momentary hesitation of crack growth at the interface. It has been found that the behavior of crack above depends on testing conditions and materials. These various phenomena were discussed based on fracture mechanics and the conditions for crack bifurcation are clarified in detail. Moreover it is found that the fatigue crack growth on the interface under cyclic load perpendicular to it could be correlated fairly well with apparent stress intensity factors of the crack assumed in an homogeneous plate and the properties is almost independent of the Young's modulus ratio E_2/E_1 of dissimilar materials.

INTRODUCTION

Fatigue crack growth in a composite materials is of great interest in fracture mechanics. Various phenomena peculiar to the fatigue fracture in composite materials have been observed in the vicinity of the bonded interface between dissimilar materials, such as acceleration or deceleration of crack growth rate, halt or hesitation at the interface, bifurcation of cracks along the interface and changes in the direction of crack growth. Most part of fatigue life in some composite materials seems to be spent in the crack growth in the vicinity of the interface. Fracture mechanics studies have often been reported on the theoretical analysis of a crack in composite material (1)~(7) and recently on the experiments of fatigue crack growth in dissimilar metals (8), (9), (10). Few systematic studies, however, have not been found on the fatigue crack growth behavior in a composite material focussed on that in the vicinity of the interface.

The present study deals with two typical fatigue crack growths in two dissimilar materials with a straight bonded interface; One is the crack growth perpendicular to the interface under cyclic load parallel to it and the other is the crack growth on the interface under cyclic load perpendicular to it. Specimens composed of epoxy plates with different Young's moduli are used in this

study, since they can realize the simulation of various combinations of dissimilar materials and the interface perfectly bonded together without any adhesive or welding(11).

Using these specimens made of dissimilar epoxy plates, the fatigue crack growth behavior is investigated to obtain the basic characteristics of the crack growth in the vicinity of the interface between dissimilar materials and will be discussed based on fracture mechanics.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

The specimens used are composed of two transparent epoxy plates which have different Young's moduli E and strengths. The two plates are bonded together at their one side edge. One with higher E value is the conventional epoxy plate ($E = 2510\text{MPa}$) used for photo-elasticity. The other with lower E value is made from epoxy resin and various amounts of plasticizer, casted into the molds of glass and rubber and bonded together with the above epoxy plate without any adhesive. Various epoxy specimens were machined to the shapes shown in Fig. 1 and then heat-treated to relieve residual stresses. Specimen in Fig. 1-(a) is a single edge cracked plate specimen to investigate the crack growth behavior perpendicular to the interface of two dissimilar materials under cyclic loads parallel to it. Specimens in Figs.1-(b) and (c) are a center cracked plate specimen and a compact specimen to investigate the crack growth on the interface subjected to the cyclic loads perpendicular to the interface. The Young's moduli and their ratios are listed in Table 1. Epoxy-duralmin composite specimens with the shape in Fig.1-(a) are also prepared as the specimen with a high ratio of E_2/E_1 (see Table 1). Specimen in Fig.1-(d) is a center cracked specimen of homogeneous epoxy plate of which the composite specimens consist. The mechanical properties of the homogeneous epoxy plates used are shown in Table 2.

Fig. 1 Geometries of the specimen (dimensions in mm)

The load applied to these epoxy specimens is too low as compared with the load capacity(10 ton) of our fatigue testing machine, so that a special fatigue testing method is employed for this study. Two metal plates are placed on both sides of the epoxy specimen in parallel, the ends of these three plates are clamped by a rigid plate or pin, and this assembly is fatigue cycled under controlled loading conditions. Therefore the displacements(ΔV) at the ends of epoxy specimen are controlled constant because the rigidity of the epoxy specimen is too small as compared with that of the two metal plates. The stress ratio R is nearly zero and the loading wave is sinusoidal with the frequency of $1.2 \sim 6$ Hz. Crack length was measured by a travelling microscope. The temperature around the specimen was kept constant ($20^\circ\text{C} \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$) carefully during all fatigue tests.

Table 1. Young's moduli and the ratio of composite specimen

Specimens	Young's modulus E_2 MPa	Young's modulus E_1 MPa	Young's modulus ratio E_2/E_1
A1	2040	2510	0.79
A2, B1, C1	2510	2380	1.05
A3	2510	2200	1.14
A4, B2, C2	2510	2040	1.23
A5, B3, C3	2510	1720	1.45
A6	2510	1440	1.72
AA	6800	1730	39.9

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Crack growth behavior in the vicinity of the interface

A series of fatigue tests were conducted on the behavior of the crack growth perpendicular to the bonded interface under various applied displacement ranges (ΔV), using the composite specimens shown in Fig.1-(a) with wide ratios of Young's modulus ($E_2/E_1 = 0.79 \sim 39.9$). Several interesting phenomena peculiar to the composite material were observed both in the fatigue crack growth rate and the crack path. Paying attention to the crack growth behavior in the vicinity of the interface, the fracture patterns could be classified into three types as shown in Fig.2.

Type A is the case that the crack grows straightly into the second material ($E = E_2$) across the interface. Type B is the case that the crack bifurcates upper and lower along the interface and then one of the branch kinks again into the second material parallel with the primary crack. Type C is the case that the fatigue crack terminates at the interface and then propagates rapidly into the second material.

The types of fracture pattern are plotted in Fig. 3 against the Young's modulus ratio E_2/E_1 and the displacement range ΔV . It is found that the types of fracture depend on the ΔV and the E_2/E_1 . Type A was observed commonly in the tests at lower ΔV level. In the tests of $E_2/E_1 = 39.9$, however, the crack was arrested at the interface for above 10^6 cycles. When ΔV became higher, the crack branching along the interface was observed in the composite specimens with E_2/E_1 value above 1.14. However the ΔV region where the branched crack can be observed is very small. The fracture pattern can be easily changed to type C by a slight raise up of ΔV , because the fracture toughness of epoxy plate is very low.

In the case of $E_2/E_1 < 1$, the crack in the first material ($E = E_1$) was accelerated and passed through the interface without hesitation. In the case of $E_2/E_1 > 1$, the crack was decelerated in the vicinity of the interface. This deceleration became more remarkable, the higher the ratio E_2/E_1 were. In this case, the crack grew into the second material ($E = E_2$) after some period of hesitation, if the displacement levels was low. At high ΔV level, the crack bifurcated along the interface or grew rapidly into the second material. The deceleration of fatigue crack growth rate, the hesitation period at the interface and the crack bifurcation along the interface are discussed quantitatively in the followings, because these phenomena seem to be important to predict the fatigue life of the composite materials.

Fatigue crack growth properties

The results of fatigue tests on crack growth rate in homogeneous epoxy plate are shown in Fig. 4 as basic data to be compared with that in composite specimens. The relations between stress intensity range ΔK and crack growth rate da/dN for each homogeneous epoxy plate falls on a straight line with slightly different slopes. It suggests that the fatigue crack growth rate even in epoxy plates follow the Paris' law $da/dN = C(\Delta K)^m$ in the same manner as that in metals.

Table 2. Mechanical properties for each homogeneous epoxy plate

Young's modulus E MPa	Yield strength σ_y MPa			Tensile strength σ_B MPa	Elongation ϵ_0 %	Poisson ratio ν
	0.3%	0.5%	1.0%			
2510		24.0	29.0	69.1	4.1	0.38
2380	19.8	21.8	27.7	61.7	7.5	0.39
2040	11.5	13.3	18.6	41.8	8.0	0.40
1720	10.0	10.6	17.3	36.8	9.1	0.40
1330	7.8	9.0	10.3	30.2	13.6	0.41

Fig. 2 Types of fracture observed in the vicinity of the interface

Figs. 5 and 6 show the growth rate of fatigue crack approaching perpendicularly to the interface through the material with lower E value for $E_2/E_1 = 1.05, 1.45$ and 39.9 , respectively. The ΔK_{app} is an apparent stress intensity factor range for a crack which is assumed to be in the homogeneous materials ($E = E_1$) with same shape of specimen. Solid lines in Figs. 5 and 6 shows the data in homogeneous epoxy plates. No remarkable deviation of the composite specimen's data from this straight line was observed in Fig. 5 where the values of E_2/E_1 were small. In the case where E_2/E_1 is large, however, remarkable deceleration was observed even at a crack tip far from the interface as shown in Fig. 6. This deceleration

of fatigue crack growth can be considered to be characterized by the decrease of real stress intensity for a crack just before the interface in composite specimen. It is not easy to evaluate exact K value in a finite composite specimen, although a few solutions were obtained in an infinite plate by Erdogan et al (3), (4). Experimental evaluation of real stress intensity (ΔK_{exp}) was tried in this paper on the assumption that the fatigue crack growth rate even in composite specimen should follow the law $da/dN = C(\Delta K_{exp})^m$. The material constants C and m for the homogeneous material are known as shown by a solid line in Fig. 6 and therefore, the value of ΔK_{exp} can be determined as the ΔK value at which the solid line and a da/dN constant line intersect as shown in Fig. 6. The correction factor F for the K value of this composite specimen is given as the ratio $\Delta K_{exp}/\Delta K_{app}$ and the F values obtained are plotted against nondimensional crack length a/w_1 in Fig. 7. These F values obtained experimentally for various ΔV levels fell within narrow scatter bands for the same E_2/E_1 values. It is found that the $F-a/w_1$ relations are independent of the ΔV values. This result confirms the validity of the assumption given before. Therefore it seems that the growth of a fatigue crack approaching to the interface can be characterized by real ΔK if it is obtained and that the fatigue crack growth passing through the interface into the second material is the same case. That is, linear fracture mechanics can be applied to the fatigue crack growth approaching towards the interface and growing straightly across the interface except at the point on the interface.

Hesitation of crack growth at the interface

The crack growing from the material with lower E to one with higher E hesitated at the interface in most specimens or arrested in the specimen with

Fig. 3 Changes in types of fracture against applied displacement and Young's modulus ratio

Fig. 4 Fatigue crack growth properties for homogeneous epoxy

$E_2/E_1=39.9$. The number of cycles for hesitation at the interface (N_{hes}) was counted from the cycle at which a point on the crack front arrived at the interface up to the cycle at which it started to grow into the material with higher E or along the interface. The location of a top of the crack front arrived at the interface up to the cycle at which it started to grow into the material with higher E or along the interface. The location of a top of the crack front arrived at the interface up to the cycle at which it started to grow into the material with higher E or along the interface.

Fig. 5 Fatigue crack growth rates in the composite epoxy specimen with $E_2/E_1 = 1.05, 1.45$ against apparent stress intensity ΔK_{app} .

by a microscope because the epoxy plate used is transparent. These N_{hes} values were plotted against ΔV as shown in Fig. 8. The value of N_{hes} increases with the decrease of ΔV and with the increase of E_2/E_1 value. The N_{hes} decreases rapidly where the ΔV approaches to a critical values of ΔV . These critical values of ΔV seem to be dependent on E_2/E_1 and corresponds to the ΔV value above which the crack branching or brittle fracture will occur as shown in Fig. 3. It means that crack branching or brittle fracture occurs accompanied with short hesitation after the crack reaches the interface and long hesitation occurs only in the case when the crack will pass through the interface.

Crack branching along the interface

It was observed that the crack which had perpendicularly grown up to the interface bifurcated along both sides of the interface when the E_2/E_1 ratio was above 1.14 and ΔV exceeded to the critical values as shown in Fig. 3. The crack growth rate was measured precisely and shown in Fig. 9. The growth rate of the branched crack decreased rapidly with increase of the crack branch length. The branched crack along the interface arrests or changes in the direction into the second material after the branch grows up to some extent. Same phenomena have been observed in clad steel plates(9),(10). This phenomenon peculiar in composite material seems to be very important to understand fatigue fractures in some composite materials. Further discussion on the crack branching will be done in detail after the fatigue crack growth on the interface have been investigated.

Fatigue crack growth on the interface

A series of fatigue tests have been carried out on the fatigue crack growth on the interface under cyclic loads perpendicular to the interface, using two types of composite epoxy specimens shown in Figs.1-(b) and (c) with the E_2/E_1 ratios of 1.05, 1.27 and 1.45. From the observation of fracture surface, it was

Fig. 6 Fatigue crack growth rates in the epoxy-duralumin specimen against ΔK_{app}

found that the crack grew just on the bonded interface in these specimens as if the interface was teared off. The fatigue crack growth rate on the interface was correlated with the apparent stress intensity range ΔK_{app} in Fig. 10 for practical reasons and the reason mentioned below. ΔK_{app} is the stress intensity range for a crack assumed to be in a homogeneous material ($E = E_2$) with the same shapes of specimens subjected to the displacement range $2\Delta V / (1+E_2/E_1)$. In these tests, the displacement ΔV was controlled at the both ends of CCT specimen (Fig.1-b) or at the load line of a CT specimen (Fig.1-c). The ΔK_{app} value decreases with extension of the crack length in composite CT specimens and increases in composite CCT specimens. In spite of the difference in the type of specimens, all of the data of the ΔK_{app} - da/dN relations for three kinds of composite specimens with E_2/E_1 of 1.05, 1.27 and 1.45 fell within a scatter band. A set of data for each test condition seems to follow the law $da/dN = C(\Delta K_{app})^m$ respectively and this property seems to be almost independent of the E_2/E_1 as far as the materials with E_2 are same. This suggests that a bonded interface has a peculiar resistance to the fatigue crack growth different from the resistance of each homogeneous material of which the composite specimens are composed. It is found that the slope of the ΔK_{app} - da/dN relations in Fig. 10 is much steeper and the da/dN is much higher than those in homogeneous materials (see Fig. 4). These results mean that the region of ΔK_{app} where the stable fatigue crack growth on the interface can be observed is very narrow and the threshold condition for crack growth ΔK_{th} will practically exist even in this case.

Williams(1) and Erdogan(2) have analyzed a crack on the interface of dissimilar materials in a infinite plate and found that the stress components σ_{ij} in the vicinity of crack tip posses an oscillatory character as follow.

$$\sigma_{ij} \propto r^{-1/2} [K_{IB} \cos(\lambda \log \frac{r}{\ell}) + K_{IIB} \sin(-\lambda \log \frac{r}{\ell})]$$

where r is a distance from the crack tip and ℓ is a crack length. λ is a function of E_2/E_1 . K_{IB} and K_{IIB} are bi-material stress intensity for mode I and II,

Fig. 7 Correction factors obtained experimentally by the fatigue crack growth rates.

Fig. 8 Hesitation cycles at the interface.

respectively, different from those in homogeneous material. Sawyer and Anderson(6) have analyzed the same problem in a finite plate by means of collocation procedure and proposed the parameter $\sqrt{K_{IB}^2 + K_{IIB}^2}$ as the stress intensity useful for a crack on the interface. The parameter above agrees with the stress intensity K_I in a homogeneous material if $E_2/E_1=1$ and $K_{IIB}=0$, and it does not have the oscillatory character. They also gave the values of the parameter in the specimen similar to our specimen. From their results, $\sqrt{K_{IB}^2 + K_{IIB}^2}$ values in dissimilar materials can be approximated by apparent stress intensity K_{app} in homogeneous material as far as the E_2/E_1 is small. In the present tests, the E_2/E_1 value is not so large that $\sqrt{K_{IB}^2 + K_{IIB}^2} = K_{app}$ within the error of 1%. For this reason, the fatigue crack growth rate on the interface was considered to be correlated well with ΔK_{app} as shown in Fig. 10. This arrangement by ΔK_{app} seems to be very useful and practical to understand the fatigue crack growth on the interface in comparison with that in homogeneous plate.

DISCUSSION

The important phenomenon of the crack branching along the interface is discussed in the followings. This phenomenon has been observed in the previous works(8), (9), (10) and, however, no quantitative explanations have not been done, because it is difficult to analyze such a crack along the interface.

The branched crack in an infinite homogeneous plate with the shape similar to that observed in this study has been analyzed by authors by means of conformal mapping procedure(12), (13). Fig. 11 shows the stress intensity factors for the branched crack with single or double branches at the end of main crack in an infinite homogeneous plate. The variations of K_I with branch length in Fig. 11 suggest the rapid decrease of the fatigue crack growth along the interface obtained in Fig. 9 and the increase of K_{II}/K_I ratio in Fig. 11 seems to explain the phenomenon that the crack kinked again into the second material after the crack grew along the interface to some extent. This crack growth along the interface is under mixed mode condition of K_I and K_{II} and, however, the crack grows straightly guided by the interface as far as a branch crack is small or K_{II}/K_I is not so large. This was confirmed in another paper (14) where the crack grew along the interface inclined to the loading direction in the same materials.

Fig. 9 Variation of growth rate for the crack branched along the interface with the crack length of the branch.

Fig. 10 Fatigue crack growth properties on the interface of various dissimilar epoxy specimens against apparent stress intensity

It was also found that the crack growth rates could be correlated well with ΔK_{app} for mode I in homogeneous plate (14).

This fatigue crack growth along the interface seems to be due to the weakness of the interface against the fatigue crack growth as shown in Fig. 10. It is considered that the crack which reached the interface should grow along the interface if the necessary condition for a crack to grow along the interface is satisfied. This condition can be considered as follows. Apparent stress intensity factor ΔK_{app} for a crack just after it begins to grow along the interface should exceed to the threshold condition ΔK_{th} for the crack growth along the interface. If the applied displacement is small, this ΔK_{app} value can not exceed to the value ΔK_{th} or exceeds slightly to it and, therefore, a branched crack can not grow along the interface because the ΔK_{app} decreases with the increase of the crack length. The crack tip at the interface has a singularity different from $r^{-1/2}$, similar to that at the tip of sharp notch(3). Therefore the crack initiates into the second materials after some hesitation cycles at the interface in this case. On the other hand, if the applied displacement is higher than some critical values, ΔK_{app} exceeds to $1.2 \sim 1.5 \Delta K_{th}$ value and the branched crack can grow along the interface after short hesitation. Thus the reason why the crack branched along the interface at high displacement range as shown in Fig. 3 was explained by the results in Fig. 10 and 11.

Fig. 11 Stress intensity factor for branched crack in an infinite homogeneous plate

CONCLUSIONS

Experimental procedures have been developed to simulate the fatigue crack growth in composite materials with use of dissimilar epoxy plate specimen with a straight interface. Basic characteristics of the fatigue crack growth in the vicinity of the interface have been obtained for various test conditions and specimens. Especially, the hesitation and the bifurcation of the crack at the interface, which seem to be important in the fatigue fracture of composite materials, have been investigated in detail and discussed based on fracture mechanics. Moreover the fatigue crack growth on the interface under cyclic load normal to the interface have also been investigated. It is found that the interface has peculiar resistant against the fatigue crack growth.

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